

The Psalm Project

Discovering the Spiritual World through the Psalms

Psalm Twelve

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The Goal of this project:

This research project will examine the 150 psalms for the spiritual awareness each Psalm offers. Each Psalm will be examined by its language and the commentary of the Sages. The spiritual awareness analysis will be done in alignment with Ari's definition of the Tree of life, the Book of Creation, and the Zohar. Each verse of the Psalm will be rewritten using the intent of the language and spiritual commentary to convey its spiritual lesson.

The Main Resources:

The Zohar

The Book of Creation

Ari's writing on the Tree of Life and the Ten Sefirot

The Theological Wordbook of the Old Testament

Samson Hirsch's commentary on the Psalms

Tehillim – Psalms – A new translation with a commentary anthologized from the Talmudic and rabbinic sources

Accordance Bible Software

Psalm 12

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
<p>For the choir director; upon an eight-stringed lyre. A Psalm of David</p>	<p>לְמִנְצַחַת עַל־הַשְּׁמִינִית Psa. 12:1</p>
<p>Psa. 12:1 Help, LORD, for the godly man ceases to be,</p>	<p>מִזְמוֹר לְדָוִד : 2 הוֹשִׁיעָה יְהוָה כִּי־גִמַּר חֲסִיד כִּי־פָסוּ אֱמוּנֵים מִבְּנֵי אָדָם : 3 שְׁוֹא אִידְבְּרוּ אִישׁ אֶת־רַעְהוּ שִׁפְתַי חֲלָקוֹת בְּלֵב וּלְבַב יִדְבְּרוּ : 4 יִכְרַת יְהוָה כָּל־שִׁפְתָי חֲלָקוֹת לְשׁוֹן מִדְּבַר־תְּהִלָּה : 5 אֲשֶׁר אָמְרוּ אֶל־שִׁנְנוּ נְגַבִּיר שִׁפְתֵינוּ אֶתְנוּ מִי אֲדוֹן לָנוּ : 6 מִשְׁדֵּר עֲנִיִּים מֵאֲנָקַת אֲבִיּוֹנִים עַתָּה אֲקוּם יֹאמֶר יְהוָה אֲנִישִׁית בְּיַשְׁע יְפִיתָ לֹו : 7 אֲמַרְוֹת יְהוָה אֲמַרְוֹת טְהֻרֹת כַּסֵּף צְרוּף בְּעֵלִיל לְאָרֶץ מִזְקָק שִׁבְעָתַיִם : 8 אֶתְהִי־יְהוָה תִּשְׁמְרֵם תִּצְרְנוּ אִמֵּן תִּדְרוֹר זֶו לְעוֹלָם : 9 סָבִיב רַשְׁעִים יִתְהַלְכוּן כְּרָם זֵלֹוֹת לְבַנֵּי אָדָם :</p>
<p>For the faithful disappear from among the sons of men.</p>	
<p>2 They speak falsehood to one another;</p>	
<p>With flattering lips and with a double heart they speak.</p>	
<p>3 May the LORD cut off all flattering lips,</p>	
<p>The tongue that speaks great things;</p>	
<p>4 Who have said, "With our tongue we will prevail;</p>	
<p>Our lips are our own; who is lord over us?"</p>	
<p>5 "Because of the devastation of the afflicted, because of the groaning of the needy,</p>	
<p>Now I will arise," says the LORD; "I will set him in the safety for which he longs."</p>	
<p>Psa. 12:6 The words of the LORD are pure words;</p>	
<p>As silver tried in a furnace on the earth, refined seven times.</p>	
<p>7 You, O LORD, will keep them; You will preserve him from this generation forever.</p>	
<p>8 The wicked strut about on every side</p>	
<p>When vileness is exalted among the sons of men.</p>	

Targum

Psa. 12:1 For praise, on the lyre of eight strings. A hymn of David. ² Redeem, O LORD, for the good are annihilated; for the faithful have ceased from the sons of men. ³ They speak lies, each to his fellow, lips are flattering; in their heart they deceive, and with a lying heart they speak. ⁴ The LORD will destroy from the world all flattering lips, the tongue that speaks arrogance. ⁵ Those who deny the essence, who say, "By our tongue we shall prevail, our lips are with us, who is our master?" ⁶ Because of the oppression of the poor, because of the cry of the needy, now I will arise, says the LORD; I will give redemption to my people, but against the wicked I will give testimony of evil. ⁷ The words of the LORD are pure words, silver purified in the furnace on the ground, refined seven times. ⁸ You, O LORD, will keep the righteous; you will protect them from this evil generation forever. ⁹ All around the wicked walk, like a leech that sucks the blood of the sons of men.

Superscript

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
For the choir director; upon an eight-stringed lyre. A Psalm of David.	לְמִנְצָחַ עַל־הַשְּׁמִינִית מִזְמֹר לְדָוִד׃

Verse Analysis

The NASB translation is not accurate from the Hebrew. A more accurate translation is "To Him who grants victory, on the instrument with eight strings, a Psalm of David." The eight-string lyre was dedicated to the truth of redemption. In Judaism, this truth is a guarantee that the LORD's help will always be available when all human help fails. The Psalm's author was in the depths of complete mental and physical exhaustion. Nevertheless, he rises on the wings of song to regain his confidence in the LORD's saving power. His struggles knowing that the LORD's eventual help is there even when the state of human society seems hopeless.

נִצְחָה (natzecha) – this word means "victory." It is the name of the seventh Sefirot in the Tree of Life. Victory comes from this Sefirot freely and is always available.

Verse Rewrite Emphasizing Spiritual Awareness

To the Sefirot Netzach who grants victory, on the instrument with eight strings, a psalm of David.

Verse One

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
Help, LORD, for the godly man ceases to be, For the faithful disappear from among the sons of men.	הוֹשִׁיעָה יְהוָה כִּי־גָמַר תְּסִיד : ² כִּי־פָסוּ אֱמוּנֵי־מִבְּנֵי אָדָם :

Verse Analysis

יִשַׁע (yāsha') be saved, be delivered (Niphal); save, deliver, give victory, help; be safe; take vengeance, preserve (Hiphil); The first word of the verse is best translated as "save." However, an even more accurate translation is "give us new life, physically and morally."

כִּי־גָמַר תְּסִיד (key gamar chased) – This phrase can be translated as "has come to an end." Something has ceased to exist and to function. The phrase implies that selfless people do not exist anymore. No more cares about the people around them.

Verse Rewrite Emphasizing Spiritual Awareness

The LORD gives new life because devotion has ceased, for trustworthiness has disappeared from humankind.

Verse Two

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
They speak falsehood to one another; With flattering lips and with a double heart they speak.	שׁוֹאֵ אִיִּדְבָּרוּ אִישׁ אֶת־יְרֵעָהּ שְׂפָת חֲלָקוֹת בְּלֵב וְלֵב יִדְבָּרוּ׃

Verse Analysis

Sadly David said that people do not speak the truth to each other. A fundamental concept of a relationship between two or more persons is that everyone speaks the truth. Unfortunately, that concept seemed to be lost during this part of David's life.

חֲלָקוֹת (chalakot) – means "smooth," or "slippery." The concept of smoothness coincides with complete division or separation. It is not possible to cleave to a surface that is smooth and polished. Therefore, there is separation because a union cannot occur. Therefore, people speak smoothly polished words and figures of speech with a double heart. A double heart means that the opinions uttered are quite different from the words that are spoken.

Verse Rewrite Emphasizing Spiritual Awareness

They utter lies to each other; they speak with division words because what they say is not what they feel or believe.

Verse Three & Four

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
May the LORD cut off all flattering lips, The tongue that speaks great things;	יִכַרְתַּת יְהוָה כָּל-שִׁפְתֵי חֲלָקוֹת ⁴
Who have said, "With our tongue we will prevail;	אֲשֶׁר ⁵ לְשׁוֹן מְדַבֶּרֶת גְּדִלוֹת :
Our lips are our own; who is lord over us?"	אָמְרוּ לְלִשְׁנֵנוּ נִגְבִּיר שִׁפְתֵינוּ
	אֲתָנוּ מִי אֲדֹנָי לָנוּ :

Verse Analysis

Eventually, the LORD will end the destruction of society because of the misuse of the spoken word. However, a social system that is based on lies will bring ruin to humankind. When this happens, evil is swathed in the cloak of goodness and truth.

Verse Rewrite Emphasizing Spiritual Awareness

A day will come when the LORD will destroy the words that destroy human relationships.

On that day, our speech will only speak the truth.

Verse Five

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
<p>⁵ "Because of the devastation of the afflicted, because of the groaning of the needy, Now I will arise," says the LORD; "I will set him in the safety for which he longs."</p>	<p>מִשָּׁד עֲנִיִּים מֵאַנְקַת אֲבִיוֹנִים עֲתָה אֶקוּם יֹאמֵר יְהוָה אִשִּׁית בְּיָשֵׁעַ יִפְיֶתָ לּוֹ:</p>

Verse Analysis

The misuse of speech to separate people will cause everyone to eke out a livelihood and existence by depriving other persons of their right to live and enjoy happiness. Some people will rise to the top of society and will force other persons to submit to them.

The second part of the verse is apocalyptic. The LORD will one day bring back happiness to everyone by eliminating the misuse of speech. After that, people will be brought together, and all persons will be equal.

Verse Rewrite Emphasizing Spiritual Awareness

Through the misuse of speech, some people control other people's lives by telling them how to live and what to do. The oppressed cry will one day invoke the LORD to bring a new life of equality for all.

Verse Six

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
The words of the LORD are pure words; As silver tried in a furnace on the earth, refined seven times.	אִמְרוֹת יְהוָה אִמְרוֹת טְהוֹרוֹת כֶּסֶף צָרוּף בְּעֵלֶיִל לְאָרֶץ מִזְקָן שִׁבְעַתַּיִם :

Verse Analysis

The LORD's assurance to humankind is through His words. The LORD's assurance is like a precious core of silver which is covered by ore and dross. In other words, sometimes, it is difficult to see the purity of the LORD's ways because humans have wrapped layers around them. These layers can be but are not limited to religious expressions and human doctrine. Therefore, every person's task is to see through the human part of religion and find the LORD.

Verse Rewrite Emphasizing Spiritual Awareness

The LORD's words are pure because they create binding relationships, like silver, when placed in a furnace, is refined by removing that which prevents one from seeing the silver.

Verse Seven

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
You, O LORD, will keep them; You will preserve him from this generation forever.	אַתָּה־יְהוָה תִּשְׁמְרֵם תִּצְרֹנֵנּוּ אֲמֵן־ תִּדְוֹר נָךְ לְעוֹלָם׃

Verse Analysis

The LORD always keeps his promises to humankind.

Verse Rewrite Emphasizing Spiritual Awareness

You, LORD, permanently preserve and keep your promises such a generation forever.

Verse Eight

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
The wicked strut about on every side	סָבִיב רְשָׁעִים יִתְהַלְּכוּן כָּרָם אֵלֹת לְבַנֵי אָדָם׃

Verse Analysis

Rest assured that the LORD knows how to keep goodness and truth separated from evil.

Verse Rewrite Emphasizing Spiritual Awareness

Lawless people can walk among the righteous the LORD can separate them.

Complete Psalm Rewrite Emphasizing Spiritual Awareness

To the Sefirot Netzach who grants victory, on the instrument with eight strings, a psalm of David.

The LORD gives new life because devotion has ceased, for trustworthiness has disappeared from humankind.

They utter lies to each other; they speak with division words because what they say is not what they feel or believe.

A day will come when the LORD will destroy the words that destroy human relationships.

On that day, our speech will only speak the truth.

Through the misuse of speech, some people control other people's lives by telling them how to live and what to do. The oppressed cry will one day invoke the LORD to bring a new life of equality for all.

The LORD's words are pure because they create binding relationships, like silver, when placed in a furnace, is refined by removing that which prevents one from seeing the silver.

You, LORD, permanently preserve and keep your promises such a generation forever.

Lawless people can walk among the righteous the LORD can separate them.

Appendix

Mystical Methodology to Prayer

All prayers result in spiritual energy which rises through the conduits that connect Sefirot realms. The "answer" to prayers is the transformation of spiritual energy from its original frequency to an appropriate frequency which will give the necessary results.

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Chambers of Aba and Ima of Briyah

Keter: prayers of thanksgiving come

MHK V1.1 6/23/14

